

Metabogenomic analysis to functionally annotate the regulatory role of long non-coding RNAs in the liver of cows with different nutrient partitioning phenotype

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ABSTRACT

Long non-coding RNAs (lncRNAs) hold gene regulatory potential, but require substantial further functional annotation in livestock. Applying two metabogenomic approaches by combining transcriptomic and metabolomic analyses, we aimed to identify lncRNAs with potential regulatory function for divergent nutrient partitioning of lactating crossbred cows and to establish metabogenomic interaction networks comprising metabolites, genes and lncRNAs. Through correlation analysis of lncRNA expression with transcriptomic and metabolomic data, we unraveled lncRNAs that have a putative regulatory role in energy and lipid metabolism, the urea and tricarboxylic acid cycles, and gluconeogenesis. Especially *FGF21*, which correlated with a plentitude of differentially expressed genes, differentially abundant metabolites, as well as lncRNAs, suggested itself as a key metabolic regulator. Notably, lncRNAs in close physical proximity to coding-genes as well as lncRNAs with natural antisense transcripts appear to perform a fine-tuning function in gene expression involved in metabolic pathways associated with different nutrient partitioning phenotypes.

1. Introduction

The rise of long non-coding RNA (lncRNA) research began with the discovery of H19 in 1989 [1] and Xist in the early 1990s [2–4]. Over the past three decades, knowledge and understanding of the regulatory power of lncRNA molecules have steadily increased. Mostly in human disease and especially cancer research, lncRNAs have established themselves as regulators and potential biomarkers and have received much attention compared to the non-coding genome of farm animals. Despite the fact that lncRNAs have been at the center of an increasing number of studies, few have been thoroughly characterized with regard to their biological function and mode of action [5].

lncRNAs have a wide range of functions in the cytoplasm and the nucleus. As summarized by Rinn and Chang [6] and Marchese and colleagues [7], lncRNAs act as repressors and enhancers of gene activation and expression and do so both in *cis* and in *trans*. Modes of action hereby include a decoy-function where lncRNAs bind to DNA-regulatory proteins such as transcription factors and thereby influence

transcription; they perform scaffolding tasks and serve as adapters for other proteins; they guide protein complexes to target sites on the DNA with temporal and spatial specificity; and they can act in *cis* in enhancer-like function on neighboring protein-coding genes [8]. Furthermore, lncRNAs can modify chromatin structure and thereby allow for as well as inhibit transcription, e. g. through the interaction with chromatin-modifying complexes [6,7]. Especially natural antisense transcripts (NATs), which are located on the opposite strand of another (usually protein-coding) gene, are assumed to impact the chromatin state and thus have epigenetic regulatory potential (reviewed by Magistri et al. [9]). Despite recognized species specificity [10], the non-coding genome of farm animals remains relatively unexplored with a limited number of studies on this topic, as reviewed by Weikard and colleagues in 2017 [11] and by Kosinska-Selbi in 2020 [12].

In cattle, phenotypic traits of particular economic importance are feed efficiency, milk yield, disease susceptibility or resistance, and meat quality including fat deposition. Baumgard et al. have stressed the importance of resource efficiency and nutrient partitioning in the

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lactating dairy cow and have highlighted the opportunity that genomics and omics-research represent for the field [13]. In the critical period around the onset of lactation, cows must adapt to considerable challenges associated with an enormous increase in energy demands. Optimal metabolic adaptation and balancing of complex metabolic and immune processes are necessary to cope with the metabolic priority of the mammary gland. Simultaneously, nutrient and energy homeostasis need to be maintained to prevent the development of metabolic and infectious diseases (as summarized in numerous reviews, e.g. [13–17]).

Studies at molecular level have focused on the hepatic transcriptome to explore the physiological patterns, changes and adaptations in early lactation [18], because the liver is the key organ that controls and modulates the metabolic and immunological adaptation in this critical time period for dairy cows [19]. Yet, so far the major focus has been on the protein-coding part of the transcriptome. The potential influence of lncRNAs on biological processes related to nutrient partitioning in lactating cows has only sparsely been addressed. lncRNAs have been shown to be potentially involved in fat metabolism of bovine liver [20], lactation [21,22], and energy metabolism of growing calves in response to different diets [23]. As mentioned above, lncRNAs are assumed to facilitate fine-tuning of gene expression, e.g. by *cis*-acting [8], and indeed, we have recently identified a number of NATs associated with regulatory potential in feed efficiency in bulls [24].

With the goal to further elucidate the molecular background of nutrient partitioning, we analyzed crossbred cows in their second lactation (F₂-population of a beef x dairy cross), which strongly differed in their disposition to secrete milk and accrete body fat [25]. Cows of the same population have been examined in previous studies for the expression of candidate genes in liver and selected plasma metabolites related to insulin-dependent glucose metabolism [26,27] as well as the expression of genes playing a regulatory role in liver, mammary gland and skeletal muscle [28]. In the present study, we wanted to investigate the liver transcriptome and plasma metabolome of the cows on a holistic scale with a special focus on lncRNAs that are co-regulated with gene expression levels and metabolite abundances. Moreover, we investigated whether the crossbred cows, which phenotypically differed in terms of nutrient partitioning, showed differences at transcriptional level to dairy cows despite their substantially lower performance level. In order to identify putative key regulatory lncRNAs, we opted for an integrative metabogenomic approach by using knowledge based joint network and pathway analyses as well as nonbiased co-expression analysis.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Animals

The animals in the study were selected from 243 cows of an F₂-population (Charolais x Holstein) bred and kept at the Leibniz Institute for Farm Animal Biology (FBN) in Dummerstorf (Germany). All animals in the F₁ and F₂ generation were generated by superovulation and embryo transfer to juvenile heifers to exclude intrauterine prenatal effects due to divergent lactation levels. The F₂ cows were kept in a free stall barn and milked twice daily in a milking parlor. Cows were weighed weekly after morning milking until the end of the study. Milk yield was recorded daily, and milk composition was determined weekly. The cows received a total mixed ratio (TMR) ad libitum containing grass (62% of dry matter (DM)) and corn silage (26% of DM), hay (6% of DM), concentrates (5% of DM; MF 2000, Vollkraft, Güstrow, Germany), and a mineral and vitamin mix (1% of DM; Salvana 9237, Salvana, Sparrieshoop, Germany). The ration was supplemented with an extra 1 kg of concentrates for every 2 kg of extra milk, when milk yield exceeded 17 kg of milk/d. Further details on the components of the diet can be found in [26]. All cows were slaughtered at the same age at day 30 of the second lactation and tissue samples including liver were taken for subsequent investigation (see below). For all 243 cows, one carcass half was

taken for establishing the carcass fat composition. For the current analysis, from the total set of 243 cows samples from 25 cows were included, which were selected for milk production and nutrient partitioning. The primary selection criterion was the energy corrected milk (ECM) yield during seven days prior to slaughter at 30 days in lactation with the fat content in carcass (CFC) and the intramuscular fat content (IMF) in *M. longissimus dorsi* as accessory selection parameters. Phenotyping and sampling strategy have been explained in our previous study [29]. The cows were grouped into animals of nutrient partitioning predominantly directed to milk secretion (SEC, *n* = 13) or to body fat accretion (ACC, *n* = 12) type (see Supplementary Table 1). The ACC cows displayed higher accretion of body fat and were characterized by higher CFC (25.3 ± 3.3% vs. 17.1 ± 2.6%), higher IMF content (6.2 ± 2.3% vs. 4.2 ± 1.1%), and a lower milk yield (29.3 ± 7.9 kg ECM/7 days vs. 190.9 ± 22.0 kg ECM/7 days) compared to SEC cows.

2.2. Plasma metabolites

At slaughter, blood plasma samples (*n* = 25) were collected and forwarded to Metabolon Inc. (Durham, NC, USA) to establish holistic metabolite profiles with 640 measured biochemical compounds. For the analysis of differential metabolite abundance (DA) in the blood, metabolites were first filtered for compounds that had less than 50% missing cases, which is a slightly more stringent cutoff than the 40% as recommended by Mock et al. [30]. For missing values, the general assumption was that missingness was due to a low signal intensity instead of no occurrence of the metabolite in the plasma at all. Missing values in the remaining 613 metabolites were imputed with half of the measured minimum of the respective metabolite as set by default in MetaboAnalyst 4.0 [31]. Out of the 613 metabolites, 563 were annotated with a unique identifier in the Human Metabolite data base (HMDB, <https://hmdb.ca/>). Group differences (ACC vs. SEC) were assessed in R with an analysis of variance in a linear model including fixed effects for year of birth and group. A correction for multiple testing was done with the Benjamini-Hochberg procedure (www.jstor.org/stable/2346101) and group differences were considered significant with *q* ≤ 0.05. Metabolite abundance for each metabolite and group was then calculated with least square means based on normalized values (*z*-transformation). Based on group means from raw values, fold changes between groups were calculated.

2.3. Sampling, RNA isolation, library preparation, and sequencing

Liver samples (*Lobus caudatus*) were taken immediately after slaughter and dissection, shock frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at –80 °C. To extract total RNA, samples were ground in liquid nitrogen and 30 mg were used in an on-column-purification with the NucleoSpin RNA II kit (Macherey & Nagel, Düren, Germany), including a DNase digestion step to remove genomic DNA. In case of persisting contamination with DNA residues, the RNA was further cleansed according to Weikard et al. [28]. Indexed, ribodepleted and stranded libraries were prepared from 1 µg of total RNA with the TruSeq Stranded RNA-RiboZero H/M/R Gold Kit (Illumina, San Diego, USA). The library preparation protocol enabled maintaining the information on strand origin of reads for later bioinformatic analyses. In a multiplexed design, the libraries were sequenced in paired-end mode (2 × 100 bp) on a HiSeq 2500 platform (Illumina).

2.4. Downstream analysis pipeline

The pipeline for the alignment and assembly of reads, the creation of a project specific annotation as well as the identification of lncRNAs has been described previously in detail [24]. Identical program versions and parameter settings have been used in this study. The pipeline has been applied to the current *B. taurus* reference genome ARS-UCD.1.2, Ensembl annotation release 97 (<https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/>

gkx1098) and the project specific annotation was subjected, as previously described, to additional sanity checks and quality filters [24]. The transcriptomic data is stored in the Functional Annotation of Animal Genomes (FAANG) database (<https://data.faang.org/dataset>) under project number PRJEB34570. The project specific annotation is available as Supplementary Data 1.

Gene expression levels (FPKM, fragments per kilobase per million mapped reads) were calculated based on the fragment counts obtained from featureCounts v.1.6.1 [32] in a strand-aware modus. A minimal expression filter was applied to all loci: minimum 0.1 FPKM in six or more animals of either experimental group. We opted for an unconventionally low expression threshold in order to capture as many lncRNAs as possible. Loci that were annotated as spliceosomal, meta-zoan, ribosomal or Y-RNA genes were excluded from the dataset.

The *in-silico* prediction of lncRNAs was performed with the FEELnc program [33] based on the project-specific merged annotation and the bovine reference genome and annotation ARS-UCD1.2 (Ensembl release 97). We discarded loci, which were annotated as the biotype protein coding and we assumed a minimal transcript length of 200 nt (default). In order to minimize the number of false positives, we discarded mono-exonic transcripts unless they were in antisense localization to another locus. For lncRNA assignment, the coding potential of transcripts under scrutiny was evaluated as well as their k-mer composition via shuffling mode.

2.5. Differential expression analysis of loci

The differential gene expression was calculated and analyzed with the R-package DESeq2 [34]. We excluded a locus (lncRNA or protein coding gene) from the differential expression analysis, if it does not meet the requirement that at least six animals of one group show an expression higher than 0.1 FPKM for this locus. An initial variance analysis indicated that year of slaughter had a significant effect on ECM (data not shown). Thus, the model for the differential expression analysis (DEA) included the effect of the group (ACC or SEC) and the year of slaughter. Loci were considered to be differentially expressed (DE) at a significance level of q (Benjamini Hochberg) ≤ 0.05 . A principal component analysis (PCA) was performed in R for the transcriptome and metabolome based on the minimally expressed loci (variance stabilizing transformation, DESeq2 package) and based on the filtered and imputed 613 metabolite values (z-transformed) respectively.

2.6. Joint pathway enrichment analysis and network exploration

For an integrative omics-data analysis, DE genes and DA metabolites (FDR ≤ 0.05) were submitted to the web-based application tool MetaboAnalyst 4.0 (<https://www.metaboanalyst.ca/>, [31]). Genes that had an official gene symbol were considered, excluding *B. taurus* specific miRNAs, and in addition, metabolites that had an unambiguous identifier in the Human Metabolome Database (HMDB, <https://hmdb.ca/>, [35]). Gene names and HMDB identifiers were submitted alongside their \log_2 fold changes between animals of the two nutrient partitioning phenotypes. For the Joint Pathway Enrichment Analysis, the Gene-Metabolite-Interaction network was selected based on the organism *B. taurus* and the KEGG (Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes) reference pathway database, version October 2019 (<https://www.genome.jp/kegg/>, [36]). Default settings were chosen with a hypergeometric test and the topology measure with the degree centrality. The applied integration method was the default option “combine queries”. The analysis was conducted for metabolic integrated pathways as well as all integrated pathways. Subsequently, we performed a knowledge-based Network Exploration with the same multi-omics data that were used for the Joint Pathway Enrichment Analysis.

2.7. Correlation of plasma metabolites and loci

To explore locus-locus, locus-metabolite and metabolite-metabolite abundance relationships, we performed a correlation analysis in R. Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated between expression levels (FPKM) of DE genes (FDR ≤ 0.05) and predicted lncRNAs as well as the plasma levels of selected DA metabolites (FDR ≤ 0.05). As for the differential expression analysis (see 2.5), we excluded a locus (lncRNA or protein coding gene) from the subsequent analysis, if it does not meet the requirement that at least six animals of one group show an expression higher than 0.1 FPKM for this locus. For the metabolites, a subset ($n = 40$) was selected based on significant differential abundance (FDR ≤ 0.05), highest absolute fold change and with regard to their relevance in metabolic processes, respectively. Furthermore, we only included single representatives for groups of highly correlated metabolites. After the correlation analysis, a correction for multiple testing was applied and correlations were deemed significant with FDR ≤ 0.05 .

3. Results and discussion

In our study, we took alternative approaches to obtain indication on potential regulatory roles of lncRNAs for the phenotypic differentiation between crossbred cows characterized by different nutrient partitioning, which were monitored at the most sensitive time of lactation regarding nutrient partitioning [37]. (i) We applied a knowledge-based pipeline taking advantage of the joint gene expression – metabolic profile analysis exploiting KEGG pathway information for network and pathway enrichment analyses (via MetaboAnalyst). (ii) We performed agnostic correlation analyses between DA metabolites, DE genes and identified lncRNAs to set up metabogenomic networks. Both approaches were used to highlight key metabolites, for which subsequently highly correlated lncRNAs and DE genes were identified. These alternative data exploration strategies were applied to functionally annotate the potential regulatory role of lncRNAs in the liver of cows with different nutrient partitioning phenotype.

3.1. RNA sequencing, transcriptome assembly and prediction of long non-coding RNAs

The 25 liver RNA samples, which were used for library preparation, had an average RNA integrity (RIN) of 8.3 ± 0.20 (Supplementary Table 2). The average sequencing depth per sample was above 50.0 million read pairs after read quality trimming. The average read alignment rate to the reference genome ARS-UCD1.2 was $98.72 \pm 0.16\%$. The project specific annotation, which was used for mapping, contained 30,806 loci and 82,628 transcripts after quality filtering. The averaged mapping rate for fragment counts against this annotation was $85.83 \pm 1.13\%$.

Within the project-specific annotation that incorporated information from the current bovine reference genome, FEELnc predicted 6161 transcripts as lncRNAs (3590 loci). For 202 lncRNA transcripts, no potential adjacent interaction partners based on physical neighborhood in the genome were found within the default window size. For all other lncRNA transcripts, a total of 19,184 interactions were predicted by FEELnc. We performed the lncRNA (structural) characterization in a locus-based manner because the expression level is also measured per locus and because a very different number of transcripts per locus would hamper comparisons (Supplementary Table 3). Therefore, the transcript with the highest number of exons was selected for each lncRNA locus. We observed an almost equal distribution of strandedness for the 3590 lncRNA loci with 50.8% being on the plus strand and 49.2% on the minus strand. The average number of exons was at 4.5 ± 7.1 and the geometric mean of the total exonic length was 1724 nucleotides.

3.2. Differential metabolite abundance and gene expression

The cow groups contrasted in this study showed a divergent phenotype resulting in different ways or priority for utilizing metabolic energy supplied from nutrients, i.e. in secretion of milk or accretion of body fat. It has to be considered that even the SEC cows of this experiment were not at the level of high milk performance of a dairy cow and that both cow groups had a substantially higher body fat deposition than high yielding dairy cows at the same stage of lactation (e.g., IMF for high lactating dairy cows at day 30: 0.9% - 1.42%, [38]). The average daily ECM in the SEC group amounted to 27.3 kg ECM, while at this lactation stage truly high-lactating multiparous dairy cows yield up to 45 kg ECM and beyond [38].

The different plasma metabolomic and the hepatic transcriptomic patterns of both cow groups characterize these two different metabolic phenotypes differing with regard to nutrient partitioning (Fig. 1).

Out of 613 plasma metabolites that were assessed for differential abundance, 185 were significantly ($q \leq 0.05$) different between the cow groups. While 154 metabolites were found to be of significantly higher abundance in the SEC group, 31 had a significantly lower abundance (see Supplementary Fig. 1 and Supplementary Table 4). Plasma metabolomic differences between the animals of the two groups were clearly reflected in a principal component analysis (PCA) by the first component (see Fig. 1). The strongest positive differences between the SEC and the ACC group, based on the log-transformed fold change ($\log_2(\text{FC})$), were observed for N-octanoylglycine ($\log_2(\text{FC}) = 3.44$, $q = 2.96\text{E-}02$), 3-dehydrocholate ($\log_2(\text{FC}) = 3.08$, $q = 3.49\text{E-}03$) and 7-ketodeoxycholate ($\log_2(\text{FC}) = 2.84$, $q = 2.36\text{E-}02$). A significantly higher abundance in the SEC group was also observed for a plentitude of lipid metabolites. The most reduced plasma levels in this group were detected for 3-phosphoglycerate ($\log_2(\text{FC}) = -2.33$, $q = 3.94\text{E-}02$) and homoarginine ($\log_2(\text{FC}) = -2.12$, $q = 5.19\text{E-}05$). Plasma levels of a number of amino acids were also lower in SEC animals (see Supplementary Fig. 1 and Supplementary Table 4).

In the hepatic transcriptomic patterns of both cow groups, a total of 18,363 loci were found to exceed the minimum expression limit (≥ 0.1 FPKM in at least six animals of one phenotypic group). A total of 2114 loci were differentially expressed (DE) at a significance threshold of an adjusted p -value ($\text{FDR} \leq 0.05$) between the different phenotypic groups. Thereof, 247 loci, which encompassed a total of 469 transcripts, were characterized as lncRNAs. Among the genes with most prominent DE status, i.e. the lowest adjusted p -value (FDR) and the highest \log_2 fold change, were *FGF21* ($\log_2(\text{FC}) = 5.80$, $\text{FDR} = 8.51\text{E-}16$), *MFS2A* ($\log_2(\text{FC}) = 3.43$, $\text{FDR} = 1.34\text{E-}16$), *ANGPTL4* ($\log_2(\text{FC}) = 2.83$, $\text{FDR} = 4.85\text{E-}11$), *APOA4* ($\log_2(\text{FC}) = 2.56$, $\text{FDR} = 4.06\text{E-}12$), *LIPG* ($\log_2(\text{FC}) = 4.12$, $\text{FDR} = 1.23\text{E-}07$), *ADIPOR2* ($\log_2(\text{FC}) = 1.39$, $\text{FDR} = 6.77\text{E-}14$), and *SLC25A47* ($\log_2(\text{FC}) = 1.68$, $\text{FDR} = 1.19\text{E-}13$), all indicating higher gene expression levels in the SEC compared to the ACC group. The annotated genes with particular low abundance in cows of a SEC versus ACC type were *REC8* ($\log_2(\text{FC}) = -4.83$, $\text{FDR} = 3.99\text{E-}04$), *HBB* ($\log_2(\text{FC}) = -4.23$, $\text{FDR} = 3.07\text{E-}09$), and *ALAS2* ($\log_2(\text{FC}) = -4.17$, $\text{FDR} = 1.86\text{E-}05$).

3.3. Joint pathway enrichment analysis and network exploration

For functional interpretation of metabolomics and transcriptomic data with special emphasis on lncRNA function associated with different cow phenotypes, we used the joint gene expression – metabolic profile data for network and pathway enrichment exploration. A total of 175 DA HMDB identifiers of metabolites and 1644 DE gene symbols were submitted alongside their respective \log_2 fold changes between cow groups to the MetaboAnalyst tool. The Network Exploration Analysis yielded to two gene-metabolite interaction subnetworks.

Subsequent enrichment analysis of the complex subnetwork 1 (Fig. 2) using MetaboAnalyst resulted in 16 significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) enriched KEGG pathways (Supplementary Table 5) with the lowest p -values for arginine biosynthesis ($p = 1.86\text{E-}04$), linoleic acid metabolism ($p = 3.3\text{E-}04$), and glycine, serine and threonine metabolism ($p = 4.18\text{E-}$

Fig. 1. Principal Component Analyses (PCA) based on the metabolome (613 metabolites) and on the transcriptome (18,363 loci) for 25 cows of divergent milk yield and fat deposition (grouped into animals of milk secretion type in blue and animals of body fat accretion type in green). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. Gene-Metabolite Subnetwork 1 from MetaboAnalyst Network Exploration analysis based on DE genes and DA metabolites between cows differing with regard to nutrient partitioning. Circles represent genes and metabolites are marked by light blue squares. Degree reflects the number of connections to other nodes in a network (small symbol size = low degree, larger symbol size = higher degree), and betweenness centrality measure reflects the number of shortest paths going through the node (nodes between or connecting networks have high between centrality measures although they might be low in degree themselves). Gene colour is proportional to the betweenness centrality value (0 = light yellow, medium = orange, and high = red). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

04). In this network, the metabolites palmitic acid, arachidonic acid, linoleic acid, ornithine, arginine and sphingomyelin (d18:1/18:0) occupy central hub positions. At gene level, *AGTR1*, *P2RY1*, *CYP2E1*, *APOA1*, *CYP3A4*, *CYP4A22*, *GNA14* and *GAA* display the highest number of connections to other nodes in the network (Fig. 2). Subnetwork 2 (not shown) contained merely three metabolites and two genes and a KEGG-based enrichment analysis of these five components indicated a significant enrichment for the pyrimidine metabolism ($p = 4.76E-03$).

The Joint Pathway Enrichment Analysis for metabolic pathways (Fig. 3, Supplementary Table 6) yielded significant ($p \leq 0.05$) pathway enrichments with highest pathway impact (PI) for phenylalanine, tyrosine and tryptophan biosynthesis ($-\log(p) = 1.61$, $PI = 2.4$). Enriched pathways with the lowest p -values were glycerolipid metabolism ($-\log(p) = 6.81$, $PI = 1.06$) and arginine biosynthesis ($-\log(p) = 6.88$, $PI = 1.31$). When all KEGG pathways were included in the Joint Pathway Enrichment Analysis, the pathways with lowest p -values were protein processing in endoplasmic reticulum ($-\log(p) = 11.93$, $PI = 0.24$), PPAR signaling pathway ($-\log(p) = 8.02$, $PI = 1.68$), and again arginine biosynthesis ($-\log(p) = 6.88$, $PI = 1.8$). The retinol metabolism scored highest with regard to PI in this analysis ($-\log(p) = 1.64$, $PI = 2.44$).

3.4. Correlations of plasma metabolites and loci

Due to the known species-specificity of lncRNAs and the scarce knowledge on lncRNAs in non-model organisms represented in public data bases, we also followed an agnostic, purely data guided pipeline complementary to the (KEGG) pathway based, knowledge-based data analysis to set up metabogenomic networks of DA metabolites, DE genes and identified lncRNAs. For this, correlation coefficients were calculated for the transcriptome and metabolome as follows: locus – locus correlations, locus – metabolite correlations, and metabolite – metabolite correlations. Out of the 185 DA metabolites, 40 were chosen for the correlation analysis (see Supplementary Table 4). Overall, the Pearson correlation analyses between 3492 loci (1866 DE genes and all 2076 minimally expressed lncRNAs) and 40 selected DA metabolites yielded a total of 1,100,147 significant correlations ($FDR \leq 0.05$) and of them 63,541 with a correlation coefficient $|r| \geq 0.8$ (Supplementary Tables 7 and 8). Of all significant correlations, more than half of the connections (55.15%) were between loci that were classified as non-lncRNAs (Supplementary Tables 7 and 8). Between the DA metabolites and lncRNAs a total of 8300 significant correlations were calculated, of which 222 showed a higher strength (correlation coefficient $|r| \geq 0.8$), (Fig. 4).

These strong correlations involved 25 metabolites and 86 lncRNAs.

Fig. 3. Bubble plots showing enriched metabolic (A) and all (B) pathways from a Joint Pathway Enrichment Analysis in MetaboAnalyst 4.0 based on DA plasma metabolites and DE genes in the hepatic transcriptome from cows with different nutrient partitioning phenotype. Bubble colour shifts from white to red with increasing $-\log_{10}(p)$ -value and bubble size increases with pathway impact. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Among them were metabolites that had connections to over 10 lncRNAs: glycine, stearate (18:0), bilirubin (Z,Z), linoleate (18:2n6), tigloylglycine, palmitate (16:0), cytidine, N-octanoylglycine, and oleoylcarnitine (C18:1). The co-expression network visualization (Fig. 4) highlights that lncRNAs in the center with higher connectivity, i.e. connections to multiple nodes, were also DE between the two phenotypic groups. The higher proportion of significant correlations between genes and metabolites compared to lncRNAs and metabolites might be due to the fact that genes had to be DE while lncRNAs only needed to pass the minimal expression threshold (with 247 lncRNAs being DE).

3.5. lncRNAs co-expressed with central players in lipid, glucose and energy metabolism may regulate hepatic glucose and lipid homeostasis and energy balance

Results from the Joint Pathway Enrichment and Network analysis indicated that the biological pathways associated with lipid metabolism belong to the major biological processes that differentiate the cow groups characterized by divergent nutrient partitioning (Fig. 3). In the PPAR-signaling pathway, which is clearly enriched in the SEC cows ($\log(p) = 8.02$, $PI = 1.68$), we found a number of DE genes encoding proteins with impact on fatty acid uptake and activation, intracellular fatty acid binding, mitochondrial and peroxisomal fatty acid oxidation, ketogenesis, triglyceride turnover, lipid droplet biology, gluconeogenesis and bile synthesis (Supplementary Table 3, Supplementary Fig. 3). Among them are for example, *SLC27A1*, *FABP4*, *FABP5*, *ACSL1*, *CPT1A*, *ANGPTL4*, *CYP4A1*, *CYP4A22*, *PLIN4*, *PLIN2*, *APOA1*, *APOA5*, *GK*, *PCK1* and *RXRG*.

Due to its interactive function in PPAR signaling, particularly *RXRG* encoding the retinoic protein receptor G could play a critical upstream regulatory role in modulating the biological processes of lipid and glucose metabolism in the liver of SEC and ACC cows. Functionally, *RXRG* acts as a master regulator by producing various physiological effects by activating multiple nuclear receptor complexes. *RXRG* can regulate gene expression in a ligand-dependent manner and in cooperative interaction with nuclear transcription factors such as *PPARA* and

PPARG. Their activation leads to a reduction of freely circulating triglycerides in the plasma and increases the uptake of free fatty acids and further impacts the glucose metabolism as well as the insulin sensitivity [39]. Park et al. [40] reported that *RXRG* may play an important role in tight control of glucose metabolism in the fasting/feeding cycle. In our study, *RXRG* displayed highly different hepatic transcript levels between both cow groups and showed in agreement with the enriched pathways exceptionally high wiring to levels of lncRNAs, DA metabolites, and DE genes involved in lipid metabolism. The 17 correlated DA metabolites (Supplementary Table 7), out of all 40 DA metabolites included in the correlation analysis, were, as expected, predominantly fatty acids (palmitate (16:0), stearate (18:0), linoleate (18:2n6), oleoylcarnitine (C18:1)), but also hydroxybutyrate and bilirubin (Z,Z). *RXRG* expression was strongly correlated with that of 796 protein coding genes (Supplementary Table 3), of which the highest correlated genes were those involved in PPAR signaling-mediated lipid, glucose and energy metabolism (see above). Further correlations were found with *MLYCD*, *SLC25A20* and *ACADVL* (fatty acid oxidation), *MPC1* and *PC* (Pyruvate and energy metabolism, TCA cycle/gluconeogenesis), *ELOVL5* (fatty acid (PUFA) biosynthesis), *SLC22A5* (carnitine transport), *LIPG* and *CREB3L3* (lipid metabolism), *ABCD3* (fatty acid transport and bile acid synthesis) and *FGF21* (metabolic regulation, see below).

Surprisingly, the highest correlation of *RXRG* expression level was found with *LDHA* expression together with a yet unannotated *LDHA* isoform transcript (ENSBTAG00000016688) and the unannotated lncRNA XLOC_019740, an antisense transcript to *LDHA*. All loci were differentially expressed between both cow groups, which indicates a link of *RXRG* to anaerobic glycolysis. In total, *RXRG* transcript level was correlated with that of 202 lncRNAs ($FDR \leq 0.05$), 89 of which were DE between the cow groups. Inspection of their genomic position revealed that several lncRNAs are located adjacently and mostly in antisense direction to protein coding genes, which are known to be associated with PPAR signaling and to play important roles in glucose, lipid or energy metabolism. One example is the lncRNA XLOC_016136 with an expression highly correlated with that of *RXRG*. It is located antisense to *ELOVL5*, both potentially interacting loci were DE between cow groups.

Fig. 4. Interaction network between differentially abundant metabolites (red nodes) that were significantly and strongly ($FDR \leq 0.05$, $|r| \geq 0.8$) correlated with lncRNAs (black nodes). LncRNAs that are significantly DE ($FDR \leq 0.05$) between cows of different nutrient partitioning phenotype are highlighted in diamond shape. Node size reflects degree (number of connections to other nodes) and edge colour indicates correlation direction (positive = green, negative = red). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Another example is the natural antisense lncRNA XLOC_018898 to *ACSL1*. Both loci strongly correlated with *RXRG* at expression level and were DE between the two phenotypic groups. Of the remaining ones, the following lncRNAs also need to be mentioned: lncRNA XLOC_015138 with its potential antisense interaction partner gene *SLC25A47* and lncRNA XLOC_028970 that is located antisense to *MPC1*. As shown in Fig. 4, lncRNA XLOC_028970 displays a central hub position in the interaction network between DA metabolites and lncRNAs. Based on the observed correlations to *RXRG* at expression level, the similarities in the differential hepatic expression of *RXRG*, lncRNAs and interacting partner genes and the differences in metabolite abundance between phenotypically different cow groups, it can be assumed that the addressed lncRNAs could play a modulating, possibly fine-tuning role in the expression of their potential partner genes in conjunction with *RXRG* in the PPAR signaling pathway.

In our transcriptome study, *FGF21* was one of the most DE genes in the liver of cows differing in their nutrient partitioning phenotype ($FDR = 8.51E-16$; $\log_2(FC) = 5.8$, see Supplementary Fig. 2). As mentioned

above, *FGF21* expression level showed a significant correlation to *RXRG* expression ($|r| 0.76$, $FDR = 6.7E-04$). In our metabolomics analysis, *FGF21* transcript level was significantly correlated with the abundance of 24 out of 40 of the DA metabolites included in the correlation analysis. Among them are those metabolites with the highest connectivity in the lncRNA-metabolite co-expression network (e.g., oleoylcarnitine (C18:1), palmitate (16:0), bilirubin (Z,Z), linoleate (18:2n6), stearate (18:0)). Except for ornithine, arginine and carnitine, all metabolites displayed a positive correlation with *FGF21* transcript abundance (see Supplementary Table 9). In addition, *FGF21* transcript level showed significant correlations with multiple DE transcript loci of the liver transcriptome ($n = 1.370$, $FDR \leq 0.05$) including numerous genes involved in fatty acid and lipid metabolism (e.g., *APOA1*, *LIPG*, *ELOVL2*, *GPAT3*) and also with the expression level of *CREB3L3*, which encodes a transcription factor controlling *FGF21* expression and its plasma level in cooperation with PPARA (e.g., [41]). Of the DE loci correlating to *FGF21* expression level are 410 lncRNAs, comprising more than the average number of significant correlations observed in our study. Strong

transcript correlations ($|r| \geq 0.8$) were observed for 29 lncRNAs out of a list with 131 loci in total (Supplementary Table 6).

The lncRNA XLOC_010660, which is overlapping with and antisense to *FGF21*, displayed the strongest correlation to *FGF21* transcript abundance (Fig. 5, $|r| = 0.98$), which indicates its regulatory potential as natural antisense transcript to mediate the expression of its parental gene. Interestingly, the database for human lncRNAs, LNCipedia v. 5.2, also contains lncRNAs in the human genome at a similar position relative to the *FGF21* gene, (e.g., lnc-FGF21-2). The bovine antisense *FGF21*-lncRNA XLOC_010660 showed a higher hepatic transcript level in SEC type cows and represented, similar to the *FGF21* gene, one of the loci with the strongest differential expression levels in the hepatic transcriptome between the cow groups.

Apart from XLOC_010660, the lncRNA XLOC_007781 was also highly correlated with *FGF21* (Fig. 5), although it is located distantly from *FGF21*: intergenic, antisense to and 5' upstream of the transcription start site of *SLC25A33*. The expression level of *SLC25A33* was not only strongly correlated with those of XLOC_007781 and *FGF21* but also highly different between the SEC and ACC cows indicating a metabolic link between these loci. The *SLC25A33* gene encodes a mitochondrial carrier protein that promotes cell growth and survival by controlling the mitochondrial genome and by preventing mitochondrial dysfunction [42]. Upon insulin or IGF1 stimulation, *SLC25A33* as pyrimidine (deoxy-) nucleotide transporter, is known to be involved in the regulation of cell growth and proliferation by controlling mitochondrial DNA

replication and transcription [43,44]. In our study, the lncRNA XLOC_007781, putatively *cis*-interacting with *SLC25A33* or possibly *trans*-interacting with *FGF21*, is significantly higher expressed in the SEC cows compared to their counterparts, which displayed almost no lncRNA XLOC_007781 expression. Remarkably, this DE lncRNA holds one of the central hub positions in the metabolite-lncRNA interaction network underlining its potential critical role associated with the metabolic challenge of the liver of cows in early lactation. This hypothesis is also supported by the observation that this lncRNA is only very marginally expressed in the liver of bulls from the same experimental crossbred population [24].

Central hub positions in the metabolite-lncRNA interaction network (Fig. 4) are represented by further DE lncRNAs, whose transcript levels are strongly correlated with those of *FGF21*, for example XLOC_015138, XLOC_023300, XLOC_006438, XLOC_010593 and XLOC_028970 (Fig. 5). Particularly XLOC_028970 that is antisense to the *MPC1* gene and also correlated with *RXRG* expression level seems to play a central role in this network. The MPC1 protein is responsible for transporting pyruvate into mitochondria for fatty acid oxidation in the TCA cycle and is required for an efficient gluconeogenesis regulation (e.g., [45]). Also, the other four lncRNAs have potentially *cis*-interacting partner genes in genomic antisense orientation to *SLC25A47*, *OAT2*, *APOA1* and *APOC2*, respectively, with important roles in energy and lipid metabolism.

The *FGF21* protein, known as a hepatokine with pleiotropic metabolic effects, regulates glucose and lipid metabolism in the liver and

Fig. 5. Correlation of the *FGF21* expression level with hepatic transcript levels of lncRNAs and protein coding genes involved in lipid, glucose and energy metabolism pathways and with the abundance of plasma metabolites. DE gene: gene differentially expressed between SEC and ACC cow groups at $FDR < 0.05$; DE lncRNA or non-DE lncRNA: lncRNA differentially or not differentially expressed between SEC and ACC cow groups at $FDR < 0.05$.

energy balance and metabolism in mammals and modulates many pathways in multiple target tissues in metabolically compromised animals and humans (e.g., [46]). Dietary imbalances such as nutrient deprivation (fasting or starvation), ketogenic or high carbohydrate diets, overfeeding, protein restriction (e.g. [47–50]) and conditions associated with metabolic stress such as physical exercise [51,52] or metabolic diseases (e.g., type 2 diabetes, nonalcoholic fatty liver disease and obesity) trigger FGF21 expression and signaling (reviewed by [53,54]). It has been reported that FGF21 is a physiological regulator essential both for energy balance in the baseline state and for the adaptation to changes in dietary imbalances in human and rodent species [55,56]. It seems to be the key signal that communicates and coordinates the metabolic response to reverse different nutritional stresses and restores metabolic homeostasis [54]. In early lactating dairy cows, FGF21 has been found to be associated with lactation performance and was identified as a sensitive biomarker for detecting and monitoring ketosis [57–60]. Furthermore, it has been observed that administration of FGF21 to energy-deficient, early lactating dairy cows resulted in lower triglyceride levels in liver biopsies, and plasma free fatty acid concentrations tended to be lower [61]. In our study, a higher hepatic *FGF21* transcript level in the SEC cows was accompanied by a higher plasma level of fatty acids that are known to induce FGF21 expression in the liver in order to restore the metabolic homeostasis.

Based on the results from our study and from literature, it is conceivable that the *FGF21* gene and associated lncRNAs (Fig. 5) together with their interacting partner genes can modulate and fine-tune energy balance as well as glucose and lipid homeostasis in the liver of cows challenged by changes in energy demands and nutrient conditions or which differ with regard to their physiological priority for nutrient partitioning.

Another gene most differentially expressed in the liver between SEC and ACC cow groups (Supplementary Fig. 2, Supplementary Table 3) was *MFS2A*. It had a higher transcript level in SEC compared to ACC cows that correlated with a substantial number of transcript levels of DE genes functionally involved in fatty acid and lipid metabolism, such as *MPC1*, *ANGPTL4*, *ADIPOR2*, *SLC25A34*, *PLIN1*, *SLC25A47* and *ACSL1* as well as with those of *RXRG* and *FGF21*. The *MFS2A* gene is known to be fasting-induced and regulated by both PPARA and glucagon signaling in the liver. The encoded protein, a sodium-dependent lysophosphatidylcholine and plasma membrane transporter for omega-3 fatty acids, has a regulatory function in growth, development and lipid metabolism [62]. In our study, *MFS2A* expression levels correlated with several plasma metabolite levels (palmitate (16:0), linoleate (18:2n6), glycine, tigloylglycine, stearate (18:0), bilirubin (Z,Z) and carnitine (Supplementary Table 7).

At the top of the lncRNAs with transcript levels highly correlated with that of *MFS2A* was the intergenic lncRNA XLOC_018415 that possesses a hub position in the metabolite-lncRNA interaction network and is functionlessly annotated in the bovine genome as ENSBTAG00000052009. Additional strong correlations were found for a number of lncRNAs, e.g., XLOC_022793, XLOC_004331, XLOC_028970, which are all antisense located to putative *cis*-interaction genes (*ABCB1*, *SLC25A30*, *MPC1*) associated with pathways included in lipid and energy metabolism. A pair of lncRNAs (XLOC_029365 and XLOC_028971) with strong correlation to *MFS2A* at transcript level is positionally colocalized with the *RPS6KA2* gene, which encodes a kinase that has been implicated in controlling of cell growth and differentiation. Remarkably, XLOC_028971 is the most differentially expressed lncRNA between the cow groups in our study and the transcript levels of both lncRNAs were also highly correlated with that of the *RXRG*, *FGF21* and *ANGPTL4* genes playing crucial roles in metabolic regulation.

The expression of *ANGPTL4* showed a higher level in the SEC group and was strongly positively correlated with circulating fatty acids and derivatives (stearate 18:0, palmitate 16:1, linoleate 18:2n6), oleoylcarnitine (C18:1), 1-palmitoyl-2-oleoyl-GPI (16:0/18:1)), and 3-hydroxybutyrate (BHBA), 2-hydroxybutyrate/2-hydroxyisobutyrate as well as

with expression levels of genes associated with fatty acid oxidation, energy and lipid metabolism, such as *SLC25A47*, *PLIN2*, *MPC1*, *SLC22A5*, *SLC25A34*, *SLC45A3*, *SLC25A33* and *LDHA*. The *ANGPTL4* protein is known to mediate the inactivation of LPL [63], and thereby plays a role in regulating triglyceride clearance in blood serum and lipid metabolism [64]. Functionally known as adipokine and hepatokine, it also regulates glucose homeostasis and insulin sensitivity [65]. A decreased *ANGPTL4* expression has been found to be associated with type 2 diabetes [66] and thus, it might be a branch point in nutrient partitioning. Wang et al. [67] found that cows with clinical ketosis and fatty liver had significantly higher serum *ANGPTL4* concentrations than healthy cows and suggested that it could play an important role in adjusting energy metabolism deregulated in dairy cows during the peripartum period. In our study, we detected several lncRNAs that were highly correlated with the *ANGPTL4* gene expression level suggesting a potential regulatory fine-tuning function for them.

Most highly correlated with *ANGPTL4* and with a higher transcript level in the SEC cows was lncRNA XLOC_022793, which is antisense to the *ABCB1* gene. The *ABCB1* protein is a multidrug and lipid translocase with broad specificity [68], e.g., glycosphingolipids and membrane phospholipids [69]. *ABCB1* expression is predominantly regulated at the transcriptional level. In addition, lncRNAs XLOC_019740, XLOC_004331, XLOC_015138 and XLOC_028970, which all have already been mentioned in our study (see above), have antisense partner genes (*LDHA*, *SLC25A30*, *SLC25A47* and *MPC1*) involved in pathways of energy metabolism, showed strong correlations to *ANGPTL4* at transcription level. The role of *ANGPTL4* in mediating the cross talk between metabolic syndromes, such as diabetes and obesity and cancer by modulating its expression by PPARs, has been discussed [70]. However, a regulatory fine-tuning role of lncRNAs should be also considered in this context and when elucidating its role in phenotype-driven interpretation of the metabogenomic data characterizing the different cow groups in our study.

The expression levels of the genes *ANGPTL4*, *MFS2A*, *RXRG* and *FGF21* highlighted in this study correlated with plasma levels of linoleate (18:2n6), palmitate (16:0) and cytidine (Supplementary Table 7). These metabolites also held hub positions with high connectivity to other DA metabolites as well as a number of lncRNAs in the metabolite-lncRNA interaction network (Fig. 4). It is noteworthy that lncRNAs with central network positions that are connected to these metabolites were also DE: e.g. XLOC_028970 (antisense lncRNA of *MPC1*), XLOC_018898 (antisense lncRNA of *ACSL1*) and XLOC_006438 (antisense lncRNA of *APOA1*). The strong and numerous correlations of predominantly DE lncRNAs to DA metabolites as well as DE genes with relation to lipid metabolism strongly suggest their functional involvement in this biological pathway.

3.6. lncRNAs involved in linking urea cycle, TCA cycle and gluconeogenesis

Besides long-chain fatty acids, main metabolite nodes in the MetaboAnalyst subnetwork 1 comprise arginine and ornithine (including also other members of the arginine metabolism, such as homo-L-arginine, 2-oxoarginine and glycine). The high impact of these metabolites on the metabolic differentiation between cow groups is also confirmed by the results of the top enriched biological pathways when analyzing all DA metabolites and the joint list of all DA metabolites and DE genes, which together highlighted the pathway of arginine biosynthesis. Closer inspection of metabolites and genes specified that a large number of them are particularly involved in the urea cycle and linked to it, the TCA cycle and the gluconeogenesis pathways (Fig. 6). The ACC cows displayed an increased abundance of a large number of DA amino acids in plasma compared to SEC cows. This was also true for ketogenic amino acids, but a few glucogenic amino acids showed the same pattern. Except for glycine, their abundance was consistently higher in the ACC group. It can be hypothesized that this is the effect of a limited amino

Fig. 6. Urea Cycle, TCA cycle and gluconeogenesis with differentially expressed genes (liver) and differentially abundant metabolites (plasma) of cows with different nutrient partitioning phenotype. LncRNAs with significant ($FDR \leq 0.05$) and strong correlations ($|r| \geq 0.8$) of their transcript levels with those of genes and or metabolite abundance involved in the cycles are depicted in purple-framed boxes. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

acid flux into the mammary gland for milk protein synthesis in these cows. The increased levels of ketogenic amino acids (Tyr, Phe, Lys, Leu) together with the increased expression of genes encoding enzymes from the urea cycle, suggest the hypothesis that amino acids were used for oxidation within the TCA cycle. ACC cows should be in a positive energy balance and would have no need for substrate supply for additional energy production and do not mobilize fat from their body fat depots. In consequence, the surplus nitrogen (N) from the diet [71], indicating a positive N-balance in beef cows fed a dairy diet at the beginning of lactation had to be detoxified resulting in elevated activity of the urea cycle. This is demonstrated e.g. by highly significantly elevated arginine and ornithine abundance and higher *CPS1*, *OTC* and *ASS1* expression in ACC cows. Interestingly, *N*-acetylglutamate is significantly decreased in ACC cows, although it is regarded as an essential cofactor for *CPS1* for the synthesis of carbamoyl phosphate from ammonium and bicarbonate generated by protein catabolic processes.

Bobé et al. [72] had suggested a regulation of ureagenic and gluconeogenic genes in dairy cows via glucagon due to their increased expression after external glucagon application. Glucagon is known to stimulate lipolysis, which fits the increased levels of long-chain fatty acids and hepatic ketogenesis as indicated by elevated BHBA as observed in plasma of SEC cows. In addition, glucagon has been shown to increase hepatic *FGF21* expression in cows [61], which is in line with

its higher expression in the SEC group and would indeed suggest a modulated action of glucagon in those cows. Also elevated expression of genes coding for key enzymes of gluconeogenesis (*PC*, *PCK1*) in the SEC group support the postulated glucagon action. But this is in contrast to the observed lower expression of ureagenic genes (*OTC*, *ASS1*, *CPS1*) in the SEC compared to ACC cows, which in turn appeared to be in contrast to the significantly higher *N*-acetylglutamate plasma concentration in this group. However, recently Galsgaard et al. [73] confirmed that glucagon receptor-mediated activation of ureagenesis is not required when *N*-acetylglutamate levels are sufficient to activate the first step of the urea cycle. Instead of mirroring the level of free amino acids, the elevated *N*-acetylglutamate concentration could be due to the energetic challenge in the SEC group. In calorie-restricted fed mice, Yanckello et al. [74] observed higher levels of *N*-acetylglutamate.

Thus, our data indicate that regulators different from or additional to the glucagon-mediated effects seem to be involved in fine-tuning the expression of ureagenic genes in our crossbred cattle population. In this context, we observed a large number of lncRNAs, whose expression levels correlated with those of members of the urea cycle, in particular with that of *OTC*. For this gene, which is central in the urea cycle, a large number of correlated and DE lncRNAs was observed (Fig. 6). For example, the lncRNA XLOC_009676 expression was negatively correlated with *OTC* expression, and this lncRNA is antisense and negatively correlated with *PEPD*, which functionally contributes to dipeptide

degradation and was significantly higher expressed in the ACC group. The expression of lncRNA XLOC_009867 was also negatively correlated with *OTC* and is located intergenic within the *APOE/C4/C1/-C2* gene cluster. This lncRNA is already annotated in the Ensembl database as ENSBTAG00000053946, although it has not yet been assigned a functional role. The protein coding *APOC1* gene, which is missing in the bovine genome, is located at the corresponding syntenic position in the human genome. The expression of lncRNA XLOC_003462, also already annotated as ENSBTAG00000000051368 albeit without an assigned function, was significantly and positively correlated with the *OTC* expression. This lncRNA is interesting because genomically, no protein coding gene is localized within 200 kb, which could possibly indicate a potential target for *cis*-regulation. The strongest positive correlation of lncRNAs with *OTC* at the transcriptional level was observed for lncRNA XLOC_026982, located 5' to *SLC25A23*, which encodes a mitochondrial solute carrier responsible for shuttling of metabolites, nucleotides and cofactors through the mitochondrial inner membrane [75] and is nominally ($p < 0.05$) lower expressed in the SEC group. This might suggest a possible link addressing bioenergetic pathways. As an ATP-Mg/P(i) carrier, *SLC25A23* is involved in the modulation of the matrix adenine nucleotide concentration that can affect the activity of adenine nucleotide-sensitive enzymes localized in the mitochondrial compartment in the liver. These enzymes contribute to the overall regulation of bioenergetic function via gluconeogenesis and urea synthesis pathways and mitochondrial biogenesis and affect reactions including pyruvate carboxylation, citrulline synthesis, ATP synthesis and protein biosynthesis [76].

The energy metabolism, namely TCA cycle and gluconeogenesis pathways (Fig. 6), are tightly linked to the urea cycle via fumarate and also displayed a large number significantly DA metabolites and DE genes in our study. It has to be remembered that the overall performance level of the cows under investigation, even in the SEC group, was substantially below the average-performance of dairy cows and that cows from both groups displayed highly elevated levels of body fat deposition compared to early lactating dairy cows. Thus, any conclusion from the current data on high-lactating dairy cows is limited. Nevertheless, it is interesting that some differences between the ACC and the SEC cows are in line with analogous observations obtained e.g. for Holstein dairy cows differing in energy balance/lipolysis in early lactation. Examples are the higher expression of *PCK1* [77] and lower expression of *OTC* [78]. In particular, the strongly elevated FGF21 expression in ACC cows (which show a higher level of plasma fatty acids) are in line with studies in dairy cows also reporting increased FGF21 associated with lipolysis [79]. Increased levels of fumarate, malate and increased expression of the *PCK1* gene indicate that the SEC cows promote gluconeogenesis compared to the ACC group, which is also documented e.g., by increased *PC* expression. These findings are in line with previous studies of trait-differentiated cows of the same population, which demonstrated significant differences in glucose metabolism [26].

In our study, the transcript levels of genes encoding key enzymes of gluconeogenesis (*PCK1*, *PC*) and energy metabolism via TCA cycle (*PC*) displayed a large number of significant and strong correlations to the expression of several lncRNAs suggesting their functional role in these pathways. The intergenic and significantly DE lncRNA XLOC_025024 has no annotation in the bovine genome, but the corresponding syntenic position in the human genome carries the annotated lncRNA LINC02473 (https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genome/gdv/browser/genome/?id=GCF_000001405.39, GRch38.p13). Besides *PC* expression, the XLOC_025024 transcript level was significantly correlated with 1137 DE loci and with the abundance of 33 of the 40 plasma metabolites included in the correlation analysis. This suggests that this lncRNA may be deeply involved in the modulation of biological processes linked to trait-differentiated phenotypes of the two cow groups. Analogously, lncRNA XLOC_012928, besides being positively correlated with *PC*, displayed also a significant correlation to large number of DE genes (1042) and DA metabolites (31). Of particular interest is the second

highest correlation to *SLC25A20*. The gene encodes a carrier protein mediating the transport of acylcarnitines for mitochondrial fatty acid oxidation [80] and displayed a significantly higher expression in the SEC compared to ACC cows. Another lncRNA positively correlated with *PC* transcript abundance was XLOC_019740. This lncRNA is antisense to *LDHA* that displayed a significantly higher expression in the SEC group, was highly correlated to RXRG expression level (see above), and the corresponding protein converts lactate to pyruvate. Finally, the *PC* transcript level is also positively correlated with lncRNA XLOC_028970, which was significantly higher expressed in the SEC group analogous to its antisense protein coding gene *MPC1*. The protein encoded by *MPC1* has a key function in the transport of pyruvate into the mitochondrion [81], which highlights the potential functional link between the lncRNA XLOC_028970 and gluconeogenesis and TCA cycle via *PC*. Due to the correlation with many genes in the PPAR signaling pathway including *FGF21* (see above), this lncRNA represents a link between the TCA cycle, gluconeogenesis and lipid metabolism.

4. Conclusions

In our study, we used enrichment, network and correlation analyses of our metabolomics and transcriptomics data to reduce the complexity of the huge data set and to obtain further information for understanding and interpretation, which biological systems might drive phenotypic differentiation of metabolic phenotypes with respect to nutrient partitioning in lactating cows. To generate hypotheses for the putative involvement of lncRNA modulation in these systems and in the expression of the phenotypic divergency of the cow groups analyzed, we focused on the most outstanding observed interconnections. Metabogenomic analyses (merging metabolomics and transcriptomic data) indicated an intricate role of lncRNAs in the regulatory network with potential consequences on the modulation of nutrient partitioning in lactating cows. Given our data, intergenic as well as natural antisense lncRNAs might exert *cis*-regulatory effects on genes involved in lipid and amino acid metabolism, energy metabolism and detoxication of nitrogen via the urea cycle. Due to the nature of lncRNAs, formal proof of functions will be much more difficult to obtain than for protein coding genes, because there is no protein, enzymatic reaction or resulting metabolite to be measured as a direct read-out of an lncRNA action. Thus, analyzing the functional relevance will to a large extent depend on correlation studies to be added to in-vitro and potential gene editing efforts. lncRNAs with hub positions in metabogenomic networks identified in our study would be prime targets for these future studies and should be considered more closely in the analysis of the physiological adaptation and changes in the metabolic state of lactating cows.

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ygeno.2021.12.004>.

Data availability statement

The transcriptomic data set examined in this study was already used in a previous study (Nolte et al. [29], aligned to UMD.3.1, Ensembl annotation release 92) and is stored in the Functional Annotation of Animal Genomes (FAANG) database (<https://data.faang.org/dataset>) under project number PRJEB34570. The project specific annotation of the transcriptomic data (gtf file) is available as Supplementary Data 1.

Ethics statement

All experimental procedures were carried out according to the German animal care guidelines and were approved and supervised by the relevant authorities of the State Mecklenburg-Vorpommern, Germany (State Office for Agriculture, Food Safety and Fishery; LALLF M-V/TSD/7221.3–2.1-010/03).

Author contributions

Conceptualization, C.K. and R.W.; Methodology, C.K., R.W. and W.N.; Software, W.N.; Investigation, W.N., C.K. and R.W.; Resources, C.K., H.M.H., R.M.B., E.A.; Data Curation, W.N., C.K.; Writing – Original Draft Preparation, W.N., R.W. and C.K.; Writing – Review & Editing, all authors; Visualization, W.N.; Supervision, C.K. and R.W.; Project Administration, C.K. and R.W.; Funding Acquisition, C.K. and R.W.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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